

LEARNING SPANISH SUBJUNCTIVE MOOD THROUGH MUSIC - "A DIOS LE PIDO" SONG**Kamela Marku***PhD candidate, MSc. Intercultural and Touristic Language and Communication
Spanish Department, Faculty of Foreign Languages, University of Tirana***Abstract**

The subjunctive mood presents a challenge for learners of Spanish as a second language due to its uses although that for Albanian students may sound a little bit more easy since in our language (Albanian) we have the subjunctive mood. Subjunctive mood in Spanish has a wider range of uses. This article shows how the professors may include music into their lessons and provide examples of the activities that promote linguistic skills in Spanish. The case study of the song A Dios le pido may not help only with the grammar and the study of Subjunctive mood in Spanish but may enhance their cultural knowledge and motivation.

Keywords: Spanish Language Learning, Music, Grammar, Motivation, Language Acquisition, Interactive Learning

1. Introduction

The subjunctive is used to express desires, doubts, wishes, conjectures, emotions, and possibilities. Unlike the indicative, which expresses facts and certainty, the subjunctive conveys uncertainty, desire, emotions, and hypothetical situations. Many students face difficulties with its correct application and uses for this reason starting the explanation of it through music may spice up the learning process and may capture and maintain students' attention.

2. The importance of music in Language Learning**2.1 The Role of Music in Language Learning**

According to Krashen's (1982) *Input Hypothesis*, comprehensible input in an engaging format facilitates learning. It has been proved by research that the exposure of the students to authentic, culturally related materials, for example, music in our case, helps them enjoy the lesson, stay motivated and interested. Therefore, music proves to be a suitable pedagogical tool for the teaching of Spanish because it helps in the introduction of new words and repetitive and memorable linguistic structures, helping students to acquire grammar unconsciously.

2.2 Uses of Spanish Subjunctive mood

The Spanish subjunctive appears in various contexts, including expressions of doubt, desire, necessity, and emotions. It is commonly used in sentences:

- When we have a verb or an expression that conveys desire, necessity, and influence in the main clause, we use the subjunctive in the subordinate clause.

- In order to use the subjunctive in the subordinate clause, the subject of the verb in the main clause and in the subordinate clause must be different. If they are the same, we use the infinitive:

Yo quiero ir. I want to go.

(The subject of the verb "want" and "go" is the same, i.e., "I")

Yo quiero que tú vayas. I want you to go.

(The subject of the verb "want" and "go" is not the same, i.e. "I" ≠ "you")

- Some impersonal expressions that are used to express desire, will, necessity, or influence are:

Es necesario que... It is necessary that...

Es preferible que... It is preferable that...

Es recomendable que... It is recommendable that...

- If the verb in the main clause expresses an emotion (fear, joy, surprise, etc.) or a judgment (you give your opinion about something: *Es bueno/justo...que* ("It's good/fair...that")) we need to use the subjunctive in the subordinate clause.

- The subjunctive is also used to express wishes. *With ojalá. Ojalá* is a word we use in Spanish to express wishes; it means "I hope" or "I wish."

With expressions using *que*. We can also express wishes with this formula: *que + present subjunctive*:

¡Que tengas un buen día! Have a good day!

- In these cases, the verb "I wish" is implied as in "(I wish you) have a good day," but it can also be explicitly expressed with verbs *esperar* ("to hope") or *desear* ("to wish"), if you wish to do so!

¡Espero que tengas un buen día! I hope you have a good day!

- We also use the subjunctive in the subordinate clause when we express doubt, denial/negation, or uncertainty in the main clause.

These structures nor uses are widely used in literature or music makes songs a good resource for subjunctive learning and practice.

"Songs can be valuable for developing certain capacities, but they can be many times more valuable if we exploit them creatively to bridge the gap between the pleasurable experience of listening/singing and the communicative use of language" (Murphy 1992)

According to Murphy (1992), "one of the important characteristics of music and songs for language learning is the fact that it seems to be easier to sing language than to speak it"

2.3 Motivation

One of the most difficult tasks of teaching languages is keeping students interested. The majority of the students find the traditional lessons based on grammar exercises monotonous and boring. On the contrary, music is a thing that every person enjoys and is a wonderful way of getting people interested in a language course. It should not be forgotten that language is closely tied with culture. As Kisito (2006) suggests, by teaching language we teach culture directly or indirectly. So, it is not surprising that instruments of culture

like music and songs have their place in Learning Second Languages lesson plans.

3. Best Practices for Teaching with music - Case study "A Dios le pido" - Juanes

3.1 Preparing for Class

Before introducing the song, the teachers can offer students to read, in Spanish language, the biography of the singer Juanes. After that the teachers may ask them about some important dates/events of his life.

She will let the students know that during the class they will work with one of Juanes songs, *A Dios le pido*. She asks the students to indicate what they think the song *A Dios le pido* is going to be about.

3.2 Interactive Classroom Activities

During class, teachers can use multimedia like the song video or only the possibility to hear the song. After hearing the song, she can offer the students the lyrics of the song and they should underline the new mood of the verb. Starting from this the teacher may explain the forms of the present tense of subjunctive mood and in an interactive way they may find the uses of this new verb mood.

After that, in order to practice the subjunctive mood, she may divide or just show in a power point presentations, some photos of famous and she will ask the students to form phrases using the present of subjunctive mood. The phrases/sentence should be related to the famous people shown in photos.

After that another practicing exercise may be to express desires using the subjunctive mood.

3.3 Reflecting on the Lesson

After these activities, students can resume on what they learned and write letters using the subjunctive mood.

5. Conclusion

Incorporating music into language learning classes, especially in the case of teaching grammatical structures like Spanish subjunctive is an effective and engaging pedagogical approach. Working different kind of activities, related to the song *A Dios le pido* by Juanes can create a stimulation learning atmosphere for students. Working different activities such as identifying and practicing subjunctive mood, listening the song, lyrics analysis and sentence formation through music can result in a more enjoyable way of learning

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